

Co-UDlabs

**Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research
Labs communities**

D7.5 Report on Sewer System Hydraulic Performance in Networks with Defects and Deteriorating Assets

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Background: about Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in UDS.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage research and innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

DTM	Digital Terrain Model
MIET	Minimum inter event time
SWMM	Stormwater Management Model, developed by the US Environmental Protection Agency

Executive Summary

Defects and deterioration are common in sewer networks. Often these are ignored as they are difficult to quantify with current inspection methods. It is known that defects have an impact on sewer hydraulic performance, but this impact is rarely quantified. This deliverable reports on modelling studies that aimed to investigate whether it would be possible to quantify the impact of deterioration or a defect in a single pipe within a network. Previous studies have focused on the random insertion of defects into an existing sewer network hydraulic model and then examining the overall impact on network performance. In this study we automatically placed a defect into individual pipes and examined the local and overall network impact. Two types of defect/deterioration were examined; the first was an accumulation of sediment in a pipe invert and the second was a defect such as a poorly installed lateral connection or roots that intruded into a pipe from its soffit. These two defects were selected as they are common and were thought to be able to influence system performance in different ways.

An initial case study was carried out in a small UK catchment, which had 195 nodes, 193 conduits, 3 outfalls and drained around 55 hectares. The sewer network was combined. A second case study catchment was selected which had over 4000 nodes and over 4000 conduits, over 30 outfalls and over 60 weirs. The sewer network was mainly combined and drained an area of around 925 hectares.

Defect/deterioration code was developed to automatically incorporate a defect into a SWMM sewer network model so that its impact on network hydraulic performance can be quantified. This enhanced sewer network model was used to examine the impact of in-pipe defects. In the initial case study blockages formed on the invert of the pipe were examined. Short-time rainfall time series was used to estimate the impact on flood severity. This work clearly showed that in-pipe blockages had a significant impact on local flood severity. It also showed that for some locations an in-pipe blockage at that location could impact on system performance at remote locations, but these were small in number.

In the second case study both types of the defects described above were used – invert blockage and soffit blockage. The second case study area was a much larger network. Because of the computational load in the second case study the simulations were carried out using a single measured rainfall event. The rainfall intensity of this event was scaled to understand the impact of individual defects for events with different rainfall volumes and to understand the impact on system performance of differently sized defects. The measure of system performance used was the overall flood volume leaving the system through manholes.

The results showed that in-pipe defects do impact on the flood risk performance of networks. Different types of blockages create different impacts. There is some evidence that blockages can create flooding impacts remote from their location, but this aspect requires more study. Only flood risk impact has been examined, however other system performance indicators, such as overflow spill frequency or overall overflow spill volume could be used in such modelling studies.

1. Introduction

The hydraulic performance of sewer systems is critical for urban water management, but these systems are prone to asset deterioration and defects which develop over time due to various factors such as pipe wall material corrosion, blockages (caused by sediment and artefacts such as intruding lateral connections), and structural failures. In-pipe defects, urban population growth, and the effects of climate change have heightened the possibility of system performance failures causing flooding, therefore subjecting people and property to higher than current flood risk (Van Bijnen et al., 2018; Vorobevskii et al., 2020). Understanding how these deteriorating assets and defects impact on the local and overall hydraulic performance of sewer systems is essential for effective maintenance and rehabilitation planning to reduce the likelihood of system failures.

Sewer networks play a critical role in urban infrastructure, transporting sewage and stormwater to wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and mitigating flooding in urban areas (Alshami et al., 2022). The functionality of sewer networks can be compromised due to deteriorations in their structural and hydraulic condition over time. Understanding the performance of the sewer systems is essential for ensuring the sustainability of urban infrastructure. European cities spend in the order of five billion Euro per year for wastewater network rehabilitation, a figure expected to rise as networks age (Cheng et al., 2008). Investment decisions in rehabilitation are often complicated by uncertainties surrounding the structural integrity and hydraulic performance of sewer systems, leading to significant risks in the decision-making process.

Understanding the impact of defects and asset deterioration on sewer system hydraulic performance is therefore crucial for enabling more informed and effective decision-making. This study demonstrates a methodology for analysing sewer system hydraulic performance under influence of defect formation and asset condition deterioration. The hydraulic performance of the assets within a network is simulated using the Stormwater Management Model (SWMM), Bennis et al., (2003), into which additional geometrical information is added to replicate the hydraulic performance of individual assets as they degrade or contain a defect. The vulnerability of assets to performance impacts caused by defects is examined by analysing the location and volume of flooding caused by the deteriorated pipe.

Initial work was carried out on a small UK sewer catchment, and this was done to demonstrate that the impact of in-pipe blockages could be quantified using a model representation of this defect within a sewer network model. The impact on flood severity was seen and it was clear that this approach had merit. A second case study was conducted on the sewer system in Schaffhausen, Switzerland, focusing on capacity reductions caused by factors such as siltation (distributed deterioration) and root intrusion in pipes (discrete defects). Issues such as computational speed and useability are also examined.

2. Literature review

Hydrodynamic models, such as SWMM, are commonly used to assess sewer system performance, including pluvial flooding and emissions. However, these models often assume the absence of in-sewer defects, which means the actual hydraulic performance is likely to be overestimated (Bijnen et al., 2016).

Cheng et al., (2008) developed a database application to incorporate condition parameters obtained from field sewer inspections into the network model calibration process. This tool captures defects from each inspected sewer segment and correlates them with appropriate Manning's roughness coefficients and sediment depths for calibration. In cases where sewers exhibit multiple defects, the tool prioritizes the most severe defects to guide the calibration efforts. Sediment depth estimation was made based on CCTV videos, and an assumption of Manning's n value was made based on expert experience. Incorporating condition measures into the calibration process would improve the model accuracy and should be encouraged when defect data is available.

Bijnen et al., (2012) used Monte Carlo simulations with a comprehensive hydrodynamic sewer network model (built in Infoworks modelling software) to quantify the impact of various sewer defects on urban pluvial flooding at the network level. The analyzed defects include root intrusion, surface damage, attached deposits, settled deposits, and sedimentation. The defects are represented in the model through two key parameters: additional roughness which accounts for root intrusion, surface damage, attached and settled deposits; sediment depths which account for sedimentation. Hydraulic roughness was described with a lognormal distribution, sediment depths with a beta distribution based on expert judgement. In the Monte Carlo simulations, roughness and sediment depths were randomly selected from a corresponding distribution function. The parameter values for roughness and sediment depths were input into the InfoWorks model and were kept constant for each simulation run. The calculation results indicate that in-sewer defects significantly influence the return period of flooding, the number of flooded locations, and the volume of flooding. Regardless of the sewer system type, sedimentation has a substantially greater impact on these outcomes compared to roughness.

Leitão et al., (2017) modelled stormwater urban drainage systems, specifically looking at the impact of sewer inlet operational conditions on urban pluvial flooding into account. When sewer inlet is clogged, sewer inlet capacity is reduced, which is simulated in the model by limiting maximum inlet flow. The impact of model parameters on model outputs is analysed using Monte Carlo simulations, where multiple runs are performed with reductions in inlet capacity that is randomly sampled from a Beta-PERT distribution.

While these approaches provide insights into how an asset's defects or deterioration might impact sewer system performance, defects were assigned randomly across the network, with their severity modelled using randomly generated values from a statistical distribution. Generally, the focus was on overall system performance rather than the impact of individual defects. For the same type of defect or deterioration, different pipes may cause different scales of impact on the local and overall system performance. It is important for network managers to understand the vulnerability of each asset, in order to prioritize maintenance actions and develop pro-active maintenance programs. Hence in this work it is proposed to integrate impact models for individual defects into a calibrated hydraulic model and then through simulation using rainfall events with different volumes investigate the vulnerability of each pipe. This would be based on identifying the threshold of rainfall volume that would trigger no local flooding in a baseline system and then comparing the system performance with the baseline system containing deterioration or defects.

3. Case Study 1: Initial Assessment of Impact of Defects

The Stormwater Management Model (SWMM) (EPA, 2021) and PYSWMM (McDonnell et al., 2020), an API for reading, manipulating, and running the SWMM model with Python, considering its flexibility in facilitating real-time control and dynamic model adjustments. In this analysis, a small UK sewer network was modelled and flood severity simulated caused by the occurrence of a single conduit blockage and a small number of multiple simultaneous blockage defects using the Real Time Control (RTC) setting, having converted the conduit to a Side Type orifice to open and close the link using the RTC function. The number and types of asset in the network is given below in Table 1.

Table 1. Number of assets in case study 1 sewer network

Asset Type	Number of assets
Node	195
Outfall	3
Conduit	193

The defect's impact on network performance was assessed based on the severity of the average nodal flooding rate over the event, considering the classification of Hassan et al. (2017) and Bibi et al. (2023). The severity of flooding is classified as follows: no flooding: 0, slight flooding: 0.0005 to 0.001 m3/s, minor flooding: 0.001 to 0.01 m3/s, moderate flooding: 0.01 to 0.02 m3/s, significant flooding: 0.02 to 0.04 m3/s and greater than 0.04 m3/s is classified as severe flooding. Rainfall data from the case study was used; a 25-day rainfall times series was examined and the two largest storm events selected.

Figure 1. Impact of Single Conduit Blockages on Flooding Severity Across Sewer Network Nodes

Figure 1 shows the results of this analysis shows that for practically all pipes that had a blockage there was severe local flooding impact (red). For a small number of pipes, (e.g. pipe 1420.1 that contained a blockage) there were a range of flooding impacts observed elsewhere in the network at a number of other nodes but these numbers were limited. This initial study clearly showed that the use of network models created in SWMM could be used to assess system performance impacts of defects such as in-pipe blockages.

4. Case Study 2: Methodology

4.1. Hydraulic model

The local hydraulic capacity of a sewer network can be modelled using the EPA's Storm Water Management Model (SWMM), simulating dry weather flow (DWF) according to population and a defined DWF pattern, as well as water flow in the sewer pipes caused by rainfall runoff from surrounding catchments with known characteristics and imposed rainfall. The impact of the condition of the asset can be estimated based on adjusting the pipe wall roughness, and if a sediment deposit is present, or by adjusting the geometry of an asset to replicate the hydraulic effect of a discrete blockage. When the local hydraulic capacity of the system is inadequate, water is expected to come out of the manholes and cause flooding.

SWMM is a dynamic rainfall-runoff simulation model used for single event or long-term (continuous) simulation of runoff quantity and quality from primarily urban areas (Rossman, 2015). It comprises a rainfall-runoff component and a routing module. The rainfall-runoff component represents the transformation of rainfall into runoff through the user defined catchment areas. Then the routing module transports the runoff over the catchment surface and then through a drainage system that is composed of pipes, channels, storage/treatment units, pumps, and regulators, into an outfall. It is used throughout the world for planning, analysis, and design related to stormwater runoff, combined and sanitary sewers, and other drainage systems (Rossman, 2015).

The following steps outline the procedure to create an appropriate hydraulic performance model for any sewer systems in SWMM:

- Build a digital replica of the physical components of the study drainage system using the SWMM objects.
- Adjust each object's properties according to the corresponding drainage asset characteristics and condition information.
- Draw sub-catchments based on information of the existing sewer catchments, find out catchment characteristics such as area, slope and flow length using Digital Terrain Models (DTM).
- Prepare the rainfall time series for each sub-catchment.
- Choose appropriate modelling options.
- Run the simulation.
- Extract modelling results from the output file.

- Calibrate the network model by comparing field collected sensor data and simulated results.
- Once a calibrated network model was obtained, it can be integrated with asset deterioration records/predictions to analyze drainage system performance under the influence of on-going deterioration or development of new defects.

The general calibration process is described below:

- Select rainfall events during the sensor monitored time period and then split the events into calibration and validation datasets.
- Define a reasonable range for all input SWMM parameters to be calibrated using expert knowledge and guidelines in literature.
- Work through each combination of possible parameter values, alter the SWMM input accordingly.
- Run SWMM simulations for the calibration rainfall events and extract the time series of SWMM object variables such as flow rate and water depth at each node in the SWMM output files.
- Use the extracted results and the sensor data to find the calibration parameters that have the best match for the real-life sensor data (water level and flow rate) for defined objective functions.
- Run SWMM model with the selected calibration parameter values for rainfall events in the validation datasets.
- Compare simulated results to the sensor data to validate model prediction against defined objective functions.

The rainfall-runoff model in SWMM depends on several site-specific parameters to accurately simulate catchment runoff. However, certain parameters, such as infiltration rates, are often challenging to determine without detailed field studies. In most cases, these parameters are estimated based on field data from sites with similar soil and climate conditions. However, whenever possible, it is encouraged to calibrate the model using field-measured observations.

4.2. Asset Deterioration Impact Simulation

The impact of defects and deterioration on the hydraulic performance of the sewer system will be tested by integrating a hydraulic performance model and asset deterioration and defect models. The observed or forecasted asset condition changes were simultaneously reflected in the hydraulic model by automatically changing individual asset characteristic parameters.

The following are the steps in building an integrated model of asset deterioration and sewer system hydraulic performance.

- Make assumptions of how asset condition change will affect the asset physical property based on real life cases or expert opinion.
- Integrating asset defect records/prediction with the hydraulic performance model by altering the relevant parameters of deteriorated assets in the SWMM input file.

- Justify and select the appropriate performance metrics, this will depend on the aim of the overall investigation (e.g. flood risk reduction, overfall spill frequency or volume reduction, direction of proactive maintenance).
- Justify and prepare the rainfall scenario(s) for simulation - this will depend on the aim of the overall study and the estimated computational effort.
- Run the integrated hydraulic and defect/deterioration model.
- Extract information to calculate the investigation's performance metric(s), for example in the case study, the aim was overall flood risk reduction, and the identification of zones for enhanced maintenance so the volume of water flooding from each network node was needed.
- Compare the model results with the baseline scenario of no defects to understand the loss of performance due to deterioration.

The condition of the asset could affect the hydraulic carrying capacity of the asset in various ways. In this study, the two defects tested are blockage due to siltation and blockage due to other factors such as root intrusion, or an intruding lateral connection. Siltation of a pipe is reflected in the calibrated SWMM model by changing the pipe into partially filled pipes, whereas other blockage types (e.g. roots, or a penetrating lateral connection) are reflected as decrease of pipe diameter but with the pipe invert levels remaining unchanged.

The vulnerability of the pipes in the sewer network are analyzed by examining the threshold of the blockage level and rainfall volume that would trigger localized flooding. The following are the steps to carry out the analysis:

1. Choose a set of design/historical rainfall events for the simulation and set a low initial deterioration level within the assets within the sewer system.
2. Run simulation while assuming all assets are in a condition in which the system performance is considered to be acceptable and the presence of individual defects is unknown. The simulation result of this run will set a baseline of the system performance that is considered acceptable.
3. Assuming one pipe is deteriorated, change the pipe characteristic parameters to mimic the loss of serviceability (e.g. sedimentation in the pipe, intruding connection or roots, increase in pipe roughness). The rest of the assets in the system remain in their original condition and with no additional defects.
4. Extract the simulation results and then compare the hydraulic performance (in this case study estimated flood volume at each node was selected to describe system performance) with the system's baseline performance.
5. Repeat steps 3 and 4 for every individual pipe in the system, for a range of defect levels.
6. If any of the pipe deterioration causes flooding or increases the overall network flooded volume, they are more prone to loss in performance due to deterioration. Extract information on these pipes and use this information in the next step.
7. Reduce the intensity of the rainfall, while keeping the duration and pattern same to make the simulation results comparable between each step. Repeat Step 2-5 using the set of vulnerable

pipes identified in Step 6. Examine the results and find the set of vulnerable pipes. Repeat the process until no flooding occurs at any node. This is the minimum level of rainfall volume that would trigger flooding under the initial deterioration level.

8. Increase the deterioration level. Pipe is filled from bottom when simulating siltation level and the level of filled part is increased to reflect increasing level of deterioration. When simulating other blockage types, the pipe diameter is further reduced to reflect an increase of deterioration level. Repeat 2-5 using the last set of vulnerable pipes and the threshold rainfall volume found in step 7. Examine the simulation results. Increase the deterioration level and repeat the process until flooding happens. This will provide the minimum deterioration level that will trigger flooding at the threshold rainfall volume.

This process will provide asset managers a tool to identify which pipes are more prone to causing performance losses due to asset deterioration so that they can prioritize their maintenance and inspection schedule accordingly. Also, it would help understand the level of rainfall volume that could lead to flooding when knowing a certain asset has deteriorated, so that asset managers can be prepared for potential flooding events.

4.3. Sewer System and Model Description

The Schaffhausen sewer system was used in this study. The town of Schaffhausen stands on the right bank of the River Rhine. The sewer network also drains Hemmental which is a town to North-West of the main city, which merged with Schaffhausen in 2009. The overall sewer system spans over 925 hectares with 9235 sub-catchments. There are 4421 nodes and 34 outfalls, connected by 4446 conduits. 11 of outfalls discharge into the River Rhine, while the others are connected to other tributaries of Rhine such as the Durach and Hemmentaler Bach. The number of assets in the system are listed in Table 2. The system is mainly a combined sewer system.

Table 2. Number of assets in Schaffhausen sewer network

Asset Type	Number of assets
Node	4421
Outfall	34
Conduit	4446
Weir	64

This case study section was used to demonstrate the described methodology. The main tasks that were conducted were the following:

- SWMM model construction and calibration: Schaffhausen sewer system is constructed in SWMM and calibrated with available sensor data.
- Two defect/deterioration types are examined. Coding was developed to automatically change the SWMM model geometry to reflect the defect types to be studied at specified pipe locations.
- Impact of siltation on system hydraulic performance under various rainfall events.
- Impact of other blockage types on system hydraulic performance under various rainfall events.

- Flood risk performance are examined, along with data interpretation to inform proactive maintenance and repair.

4.3.1. Model build and calibration

Asset and catchment information. The Schaffhausen sewer network was originally modelled in Mike+. Asset information was extracted from the Mike+ model, including asset type, location and geometry. Catchment boundary information was also extracted from the model. However, some of the catchment characteristics needed for a SWMM model are not readily available in Mike+. Hence parameters such as area, slope and flow length are calculated with a DTM using ArcGIS.

The 2040 sub-catchments each have an estimated population and supply a dry weather flow into the SWMM model nodes. The CIRIA standard 24-hour profile (as shown in Table 1 – Appendix A) and an estimated wastewater flow volume of 143 l/capita/day is used to simulate wastewater dry weather flow into the relevant nodes of the SWMM model of the Schaffhausen sewer network.

Rainfall data - rainfall event simulation. Two rainfall time series from two weather stations are used in this case study analysis. Dates of rainfall data collection ranged from 01/04/2022 to 24/04/2023. Data is recorded in 5 minutes time steps and rainfall intensity is reported in mm/5 minutes. Data were converted to mm/hour with a 5-minute interval that were then used in the SWMM model.

Figure 2. Rain Gauge locations - indicated by red and blue dots

Herblingen is in the main city area hence contains the majority of the sewer network catchment, whereas Hemmental is located at the northwest corner, as shown in Figure 2. The rain data from each gauge was linked to their respective areas of the model.

Table 3. Rainfall events selected for calibration

	Start Time	End Time	Total Volume (mm)	Duration (hour)	Average (mm/hour)
Event 1	2022-08-05 20:25:00	2022-08-06 03:40:00	47.71	7.25	6.58
Event 2	2023-03-13 21:15:00	2023-03-14 02:15:00	23.78	5.0	4.76
Event 3	2022-04-24 02:40:00	2022-04-24 05:10:00	8.50	2.5	3.40
Event 4	2022-08-26 21:25:00	2022-08-27 18:25:00	42.28	21.0	2.01
Event 5	2022-08-17 22:00:00	2022-08-18 03:30:00	9.93	5.5	1.81
Event 6	2022-09-07 20:40:00	2022-09-08 07:45:00	18.71	11.1	1.69

Rainfall events are defined using selected minimum inter-event time (MIET), which is the minimum number of dry hours between two consecutive rainfall events. For small urban catchments, the MIET is usually 6 hours (Essien et al., 2023). To qualify as an individual rainfall event, there must be fewer than MIET consecutive dry hours during the rainfall hours. Following this guidance 189 events were identified and extracted as a result from the 25 months of available rainfall data. The ones with the top 6 average rainfall depth per hour are used in the calibration. The details of the events are listed in Table 3.

Sensor data summary. 12 sensor datasets are available. Sensors 2 and 7 are flow meters, the other water level meters. Data from Sensor 8-11 does not cover the period of the rainfall data, hence are not used in the calibration. Location of the remaining 8 sensors that are used in the calibration are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Location of the sensors

4.3.2. Calibration results

Infiltration parameters are calibrated using the level data at the sensor locations. The optimum set of infiltration value is the one that gives the lowest Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) for the simulated SWMM data and sensor data. RMSE is one of the main performance indicators for measuring the average difference between values predicted by a model and the actual values. The objective function is as follows:

$$RMSE = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m (D_{sensor,i,t_j} - D_{SWMM,i,t_j})^2} \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

where D_{sensor,i,t_j} is the observed water depth at time j by sensor i ; D_{SWMM,i,t_j} is the simulated water depth at the location of sensor i at time j ; m is the total number of time steps. Rainfall event 1 is selected as the calibration event. The combination of parameter values tested are listed in Table 4. The selection of these parameter ranges follows the recommendations in the SWMM user guide. The interval is configured to capture a moderate amount of parameter combinations, ensuring that the tests yield enough information to identify potential values for the best fit without requiring excessive computational resources.

Table 4. The range and interval of the hydrological parameters sequence tested

Parameter	Range	Interval
Maximum Infiltration Rate (mm/hr)	(50, 150)	5
Minimum Infiltration Rate(mm/hr)	(1,12)	1
Decay Constant	(4,7)	1

The optimum set of infiltration parameters is: maximum infiltration rate – 150 mm/hour, minimum infiltration rate – 5 mm/hour, decay constant – 4. This set of parameter values is then applied to other 5 rainfall events for validation.

For both the calibration and validation rainfall events, the plots of the simulated and sensor recorded time series of each sensor location are shown in Appendix B. The RMSE (in centimetres) for each sensor location for all six rainfall events is listed in Table 5.

Table 5. RMSE of water level (cm) for each sensor and rainfall events

	Event 1	Event 2	Event 3	Event 4	Event 5	Event 6
Sensor 2	N/A	N/A	17.11	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sensor 3	33.15	10.43	5.11	12.95	7.36	3.78
Sensor 4	5.66	6.87	5.60	3.49	3.58	4.95
Sensor 5	4.77	2.99	2.07	3.36	2.38	1.18
Sensor 6	14.37	15.28	12.70	12.00	11.81	12.29
Sensor 7	N/A	N/A	8.89	9.35	7.12	1.86
Sensor 12	28.90	31.67	29.43	34.95	46.23	27.50

The RMSE results and plots, together with the information on the sensor documentations shows that:

- Sensor 1 fits better with events with higher average rainfall intensity. Since sensor 1 was recorded in time steps different from the SWMM model and the data is quite patchy, it was only used for a

visual model fitness inspection. The level of fit could be because it is downstream of three rural catchments which are more sensitive to variation in rainfall data. Also, there are discrepancies in the measured water level data, as the maximum level depth of the node is 1.58m, but the maximum sensor measure is over 1.775 m.

- Sensor 2 has a limited number of recordings, so it was not included in the calibration process. It is only simulated for one event (Event 3). Although the water level is underestimated, the fitness of the flow rate is quite good. It is possible the datum of the sensor is not calibrated well. Sensor 3 fits quite well for most of the events. Although for Event 1 the RMSE is high, that is mainly due to error in the sensor data, as quite a large section of the sensor reading remained unchanged - indicating a period of sensor failure. For Event 4, RMSE is slightly higher as the simulated water level and is shifted backwards, this could be due to regional variations in rainfall recording on the day.
- Sensor 4 is underestimated for all events. However, in the sensor data information notes, the sensor is not yet fully calibrated. Due to low gradient, the location is susceptible to silting and hence the level could be higher than modelled.
- Sensor 5 fits quite well for all events, all RMSE are below 5cm.
- The water levels obtained from sensor 6 are overestimated for all six rainfall events. The location is adjacent to farmland and is therefore strongly influenced by runoff water from precipitation-dependent agricultural drainage systems.
- Sensor 7 only covers three events: Events 3, 4 and 5. The simulated peak of the water level is close to the sensor data but happened slightly earlier than recorded. The simulated flow rate is also slightly shifted and the peak is a bit higher than recorded.
- Sensor 12 is slightly underestimated; it was recorded that gravel was deposited in front of the venturi (sensor 12 location) which might make the measured level too high.

The calibrated model generally provides a good fit for real-life situations. Although some events exhibit slightly higher RMSE values, the SWMM's results closely match the sensor data in terms of shape and peak levels. A minor shift in the pattern does not compromise the model's ability to simulate potential flooding scenarios, as only the focus will be on whether water level exceeds ground level and a slight delay in prediction is tolerable. For sensors 4, 6, and 12, which show overestimated or underestimated values, it is either yet to be fully calibrated or influenced by external factors or a known existing defect condition. The defect can be incorporated into the model in the future if more detailed information is given. For the well-calibrated sensors (3, 5, and 7) and for events with complete data, the RMSEs are all below 10 cm, indicating reasonable model fit.

4.4. Impact of pipe deterioration – in-pipe deposition

4.4.1. Assumptions

Once the model is calibrated, it can be used to simulate the potential hydraulic impacts of deterioration/defects in the sewer system. To reflect the pipe defects in the SWMM model, the deteriorated pipe is assumed to be filled up uniformly by sediment from the pipe bottom. The reduced

available cross-sectional area means that flow capacity of the pipe is hence reduced and water level entering the pipe is raised – if flow conditions are sub-critical. Although in real life, siltation or blockage is likely to be present only in a section of the pipe, for the simplicity of modelling, it is assumed that the whole pipe length contains siltation. In a SWMM model, the Filled Circular shape allows the bottom of a circular pipe to be filled with sediment and thus limit its flow capacity (Rossman, 2015).

Field observations in other networks have reported that less than 5% of the pipe had a deposition thickness greater than 50% of the pipe diameter. Most of the pipes with observed deposits have a sediment height of 10% to 30% of the pipe diameter (Essien et al., 2023). Hence in this study, the medium value of 20% of the pipe diameter is chosen to be the initial siltation level tested.

Rainfall event 3 was chosen for the simulation since it has a high average intensity so it would generate enough runoff to test the capacity of the system. Also, its duration is relatively short which would require less computational effort to run than other rainfall events. On average, one simulation of a 3.5-hour event (Event 3) would take around 30 seconds with a 24 core computer, so to run a simulation for each pipe in this sewer system once would take 37 hours. The system floods without any blockage under rainfall event 3. Additional flooding volume in each node is calculated by subtracting the node flooding with the baseline flooding volume (25% rainfall intensity) where there is no blockage. The additional flooding volume is used to determine whether siltation in the pipe caused flooding.

4.4.2. Results: rainfall threshold investigation

The analysis was carried out in several phases as described in the methodology. The minimum level of rainfall volume that would trigger flooding under the initial deterioration/defect size is determined. In this case study this threshold was reached between 25% and 30% rainfall intensity for Rainfall Event 3.

25% rainfall intensity. After reaching the stage when rainfall intensity is only 25% of the original value, none of the pipes caused any flooding with the siltation level of 20% of the pipe diameter.

30% rainfall intensity. Simulation results show that only 76 pipes caused an increase in flooding volume for this rainfall level using the rainfall from Event 3. A heat map composing all pipes with the additional flooded volume caused by pipe deterioration is plotted in Figure 4. The darker the colour of the pipes (deeper orange) means higher flood volumes are caused by the in-pipe deposit. The pipes causing the most significant flooding are mostly located in the main pipe connecting the Schaffhausen city and the Hemmental area. Since there is only one pipe connecting the two areas unlike the more interlinked network in the city center, there is no extra capacity if one of the pipes is blocked. Hence, these pipes are the most vulnerable pipes in the system. They can cause flooding even with a low rainfall volume, hence they should be inspected and potentially maintained more frequently.

Figure 4. Additional flooding caused by siltation that fills up 20% of the pipe diameter with 30% of the baseline rainfall intensity in Rainfall Event 3

50% rainfall intensity. At 50% rainfall intensity, 1799 pipes cause additional flooding when deteriorated. A heat map shows the additional flooded volume in Figure 5. The pipes that cause flooding are mostly concentrated towards the edge of the city. This is probably due to these pipes are closer to the outer zone of the network in which pipes probably have larger contributing catchments than in the center of the city. This demonstrates zones in which sediment siltation can have a noticeable impact on flow capacity.

Figure 5. Additional flooding caused by siltation that fills up 20% of the pipe diameter with 50% of the rainfall intensity in event 3

100% rainfall intensity. The simulation results shown in Figure 6 indicate that 4044 of the 4446 pipes cause additional flooding when there is siltation of 20% of the pipe diameter with Rainfall Event 3. The heat map of the additional flooded volume is plotted in Figure 5, it shows widespread flooding.

Figure 6. Additional flooding caused by siltation that fills up 20% of the pipe diameter with 100% of the intensity of Rainfall Event 3.

Examining the histogram of the total flooded volume for each defect location, for the 30% rainfall intensity event it is seen that most of the network flooding volume values is around 2 m^3 for the whole network. This means that many of the pipes with 20% pipe siltation do not cause any additional flooding under this rainfall volume. The histogram of the 50% rainfall intensity shows a similar pattern the range of network flooding volume values tightly bunched around 50.5 m^3 showing that although more defects do cause flooding, the overall flooding is minor in total and occurs at significant number of nodes. This number means that the water utility needs to focus its proactive cleaning activities in a significant number of locations. This makes the development of an effective cleaning program more challenging. Once the rainfall intensity is raised to 100% then the volume of network flooding rises by an order of magnitude and ranges from 525 m^3 to 527.5 m^3 (see Figure 6). Table 5 summarizes the total network volume and number of flooded nodes for the different rainfall intensities for Rain Event 3. The histogram of the total flooded volume for individual siltation locations is shown in Figure 7. When plotting this histogram any network flood volume value is considered an outlier if it is below the 1st percentile or above the 99th percentile of the dataset and is hence removed from the histogram. The distribution of the flooding volume, for 100% rainfall intensity is slight left skewed with a mode around 526 m^3 and a distinct peak around the 75th percentile.

Figure 7. Histogram of network flooded volumes for 20% in-pipe blockage and 100% rainfall intensity for Rain Event 3.

The distance between each deteriorated pipe and the flooded nodes were calculated, the maximum distance was shown in the histogram in Figure 8. The affected radius of a blocked pipe can range from 24 meters to 6825 meters. The distribution is slightly right skewed with the majority of the distances between the defect and the flooding node being around 4000 meters. This distribution was unexpected as it appears that a defect can impact on a location that is a considerable distance from the defect location.

Figure 8. Distribution of maximum distance between deteriorated pipe and flooded node, for 20% in-pipe siltation and 100% rainfall intensity for Rainfall Event 3.

Summary. A summary of the number of individual pipes with the 20% siltation that caused additional flooding for particular rainfall volume is shown in Table 6. It is seen that as the rainfall volume increases, the number of pipes with siltation that would cause additional flooding also increases. The relationship

between rainfall intensity and the percentage of pipes causing additional flooding is non-linear: a 20% increase from 30% to 50% in rainfall intensity results in a 38.8% increase in flooding pipes, while a larger 50% increase from 50% to 100% in rainfall intensity results in only a 50.5% increase.

Table 6. Summary of the number of pipes causing additional flooding vs rainfall volume

Rainfall volume ($m^3 \times 10^5$)	Number of pipes additional flooding	Percentage of pipes with additional flooding
73.88 (100%)	4044	91.0%
36.94 (50%)	1799	40.5%
22.16 (30%)	76	1.7%
18.47 (20%)	0	0.0%

4.4.3. Results: influence of siltation level

Table 6 shows that the 20% rainfall intensity at a 20% siltation level will not trigger flooding even at the 76 most vulnerable pipe locations. In this section, the siltation level of the 76 most vulnerable pipes were systematically increased to test the threshold of blockage size in these vulnerable pipes which will cause flooding for a low rainfall intensity. The siltation level and the number of pipes that caused flooding are listed in Table 7 below. It is seen that the number of additional flooded nodes increases slowly as the siltation level climbs to a relatively steady state in which the size of the blockage does not seem to influence the number of additional flooded nodes. This result indicates that if the vulnerable sites can be identified that the size of the blockage above the default 20% can increase without significant additional flooding. A blockage size over 40% was associated with a rapidly rising number of additional flooded nodes. This pattern of behaviour indicates that pro-active maintenance would be practically possible as if blockages could be removed before they grew to more than 40% of the pipe diameter then a beneficial outcome could be achieved.

Table 7. Levels of siltation in vulnerable pipes (76) that cause flooding for low (20%) intensity Rainfall Event 3

Siltation level	Number of nodes with flooding
30%	2
40%	6
50%	13
60%	18
70%	19
80%	20
90%	22

4.5. Impact of pipe deterioration – other types of blockage

Loss in hydraulic capacity due to other blockage types are investigated. The types of blockage considered are those that intrude into the flow from the pipe soffit such as root intrusion or an intruding lateral connection. Such blockage types are modelled in SWMM as reduction in pipe diameter, but the

50% rainfall intensity. At 50% rainfall intensity, 1337 pipes cause additional flooding when deteriorated. A heat map shows the additional flooded volume in Figure 10. The pipes that cause higher flooding volumes are in similar locations as the ones under 20% rainfall intensity. The number of pipes with the defect, causing flooding became less than with the ones with siltation at 50% rainfall intensity. This is because when there is siltation, debris in a pipe raises its effective invert level, causing the water level to rise; whereas for the diameter reduction scenario which mimics the intrusion/blockage from the top of the pipe, in this case, for some of the pipes, the water level could be high but does not reach the threshold of flooding. Hence, the impact of this type of defect is less than the impact of siltation.

Figure 10. Additional flooding caused by reduction in pipe diameter with 50% of the rainfall intensity in Rainfall Event 3

100% rainfall intensity. The result shows that 4,039 of the 4,446 pipes cause additional flooding when there is reduction in pipe diameter with Rainfall Event 3. A heat map of the additional flooded volume is plotted in Figure 11. This indicates flooding throughout the network area and is similar in spread to the pattern observed with the siltation defect. A comparison was made between the flood volume caused by two types of pipe defect/deterioration. Figure 12 shows the scatter plot of the flooding volume due to siltation vs “other type” blockage for each pipe. The plot shows that the two distributions are very similar. Statistical analysis is performed to test the similarity of the two flooding volume datasets. The mean value is 526.56m³ for siltation and 526.54 m³ for diameter reduction blockage. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the two defects is 0.989, which suggests a very strong positive linear relationship. The p-value from the paired t-test is approximately 0.418, indicating that there is not a statistically significant difference between the two datasets at a 0.05 significance level. This suggests that the flooding volume caused by siltation and diameter reduction is relatively similar.

Figure 11. Additional flooding caused by reduction in pipe diameter with 100% of the rainfall intensity in Rainfall Event 3

Figure 12. Scatter plot of flooding volume due to siltation vs diameter reduction

Summary. A summary of the number of pipes that caused flooding under the “other type” of blockage against the rainfall volume of different events is shown in Table 8 below. The results showed a positive correlation between them. However, unlike the siltation scenario, the relationship between the increase in the number of pipes causing additional flooding and the amount of increase in rainfall volume is close to linear.

Table 8. Summary of number of pipes caused additional flooding vs rainfall volume

Rainfall volume ($m^3 \times 10^5$)	Number of pipes caused additional flooding	Percentage of pipes caused additional flooding
73.88	4039	90.8%
36.94	1337	30.1%
22.16	125	2.8%
18.47	0	0.0%

4.5.2. Results: siltation threshold

Under a low rainfall (25% rainfall intensity), none of the 125 most vulnerable pipes triggered flooding with the initial diameter reduction to represent defects such as root or a lateral connection intrusion. In this section, the diameter of the 125 most vulnerable pipes was decreased to test the threshold of blockage in these vulnerable pipes which will cause flooding at the lower rainfall intensity. The amount of diameter reduction is calculated such that the reduced cross-sectional area is the same as the one under the siltation level tested in the earlier sections. The siltation level and the number of pipes that caused flooding are listed in Table 9 below. The number of pipes, with a defect that will cause flooding are all less than the simulations with the same rainfall intensity and equivalent siltation levels. This again shows that the effect of top intrusion (diameter reduction) is less severe than the bottom blockage (siltation).

Table 9. Minimal levels of reduction in pipes diameter (which would result in a cross-sectional area that is the same as the one under the earlier listed siltation level) to cause flooding in the low rainfall event (20% intensity event).

Equivalent siltation level	Number of flooded nodes
30%	0
40%	5
50%	8
60%	10
70%	11
80%	12
90%	12

5. Discussion and Conclusions

This study investigated the impact of two types of asset deterioration on hydraulic performance of a case study sewer network. This is carried out by integrating asset deterioration scenarios with the hydraulic performance modelling carried out using SWMM. The proposed methodology helps identify vulnerable pipes, that if they contain a defect can cause poor overall network performance. The integrated modelling approach was able to identify the vulnerable pipes and quantify their impact on the amount of nodal flooding across the network. The simulations first identified the adjusted volume of a measured rainfall event that first caused nodal flooding and this was used as a baseline to examine the impact of defects.

The simulation results were able to identify the locations of the vulnerable pipes that if they contained a defect would result in flooding. This number progressively increased as the size of the adjusted rainfall event increased. The pattern of increase was different for both types; for the siltation type defect the pattern of increase was clearly non-linear but for the defect type that simulated an obstruction in the top of a pipe this pattern of increase was linear. The size of the defect for low intensity rainfall events seemed relatively unimportant until the size of the defect that greater than 50% of the pipe diameter (or its equivalent).

The geographic clustering of vulnerable pipes suggests that network geometry can play a role in defining the pipes that if they contain a defect can impact on the performance of the sewer system. Pipes located near outfalls or serving as connections between the two sub-networks were more prone to cause network flooding when deteriorated, hence asset manager should prioritize maintenance in these areas.

The simulations were able to indicate to a network manager which pipes should be more frequently inspected and maintained, as these were the ones in which the presence of a particular defect would cause an increase in flood risk.

The simulations took around 1.5 days to run on a very capable PC, meaning that only limited rainfall events or short rainfall time series could be considered. If this modelling could be combined with inspection data then the simulations could focus on fewer pipe locations and so they would be able to test the sensitivity of the resulting flooding volumes to defect size and their future deterioration using longer rainfall time series. This type of simulation would provide an indication to network managers as to when they would need to act to mitigate the flooding impact of a developing defect.

This research demonstrated the potential for combining hydrodynamic modelling with asset condition data to support risk-based decision-making. For instance, the identification of threshold deterioration levels allows stakeholders to predict when maintenance is needed, reducing the risk of system failures. Focused operation investments in high-risk zones/locations can therefore yield significant reductions in flood risk.

Although the proposed integrated model of asset deterioration and SWMM system simulations provided a powerful tool for understanding the failure risks and consequence of individual assets in the system. The assumptions made in this study to mimic the physical impact of the defects may not fully represent the complexities of real-world conditions. Therefore, more work should be carried out to understand the uncertainties from the model concepts used to simulate the hydraulic impacts of the two types of defects that were studied. For example, in practice, siltation often occurs unevenly along pipe segments, and the extent of root intrusion or other intrusions are highly variable and site specific. Incorporating such variability into the model would improve the accuracy of any future simulation.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Dry Weather Flow Factors used in SWMM model

Table A1. Dry weather flow pattern (Ainger et al., 1997)

Time (hh:mm)	Factor
00:00	0.55
01:00	0.25
02:00	0.08
03:00	0.07
04:00	0.08
05:00	0.11
06:00	0.58
07:00	1.63
08:00	2.12
09:00	1.83
10:00	1.68
11:00	1.51
12:00	1.23
13:00	1.14
14:00	1.12
15:00	0.92
16:00	0.95
17:00	1.16
18:00	1.26
19:00	1.44
20:00	1.16
21:00	1.05
22:00	1.11
23:00	0.97

Appendix B – SWMM Calibration Results – Sensor data versus simulation.

(a) Sensor 1 level at Event 1 (b) Sensor 1 level at Event 2

(c) Sensor 1 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 1 level at Event 4

(e) Sensor 1 level at Event 5 (f) Sensor 1 level Event 6

Figure B1. Sensor 1 calibration plots

(a) Level of Sensor 2 at Event 3 (b) flow rate of Sensor 2 at Event 3

Figure B2. Sensor 2 calibration plots

(a) Sensor 3 level at Event 1 (b) Sensor 3 level at Event 2

(c) Sensor 3 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 3 level at Event 4

Sensor 3 level at Event 5 (d) Sensor 3 level at Event 6

(c)

Figure B3. Sensor 3 calibration plots

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(a) Sensor 4 level at Event 1 (b) Sensor 4 level at Event 2

(c) Sensor 4 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 4 level at Event 4

(c) Sensor 4 level at Event 5 (d) Sensor 4 level at Event 6

Figure B4. Sensor 4 calibration plots

(a) Sensor 5 level at Event 1 (b) Sensor 5 level at Event 2

(c) Sensor 5 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 5 level at Event 4

(c) Sensor 5 level at Event 5 (d) Sensor 5 level at Event 6

Figure B5. Sensor 5 calibration plots

(a) Sensor 6 level at Event 1 (b) Sensor 6 level at Event 2

(c) Sensor 6 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 6 level at Event 4

(c) Sensor 6 level at Event 5 (d) Sensor 6 level at Event 6

Figure B6. Sensor 6 calibration plots

(a)

Sensor 7 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 7 flow rate at Event 3

(c) Sensor 7 level at Event 4 (d) Sensor 7 flow rate at Event 4

(c) Sensor 7 level at Event 5 (d) Sensor 7 flow rate at Event 5

Figure B7. Sensor 7 calibration plots

(a) Sensor 12 level at Event 1 (b) Sensor 12 level at Event 2

(c) Sensor 12 level at Event 3 (d) Sensor 12 level at Event 4

(c) Sensor 12 level at Event 5 (d) Sensor 12 level at Event 6

Figure B8. Sensor 12 calibration plots